

ABSTRAKCJA TEKSTÓW JĘZYKA OBCEGO JAKO ŚRODKI PRZETWARZANIA INFORMACJI

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Streszczenie. Jedną z metod nauczania języka obcego w liceach nieanglojęzycznych jest rozwijanie umiejętności analitycznego i syntetycznego przetwarzania informacji w uczących się języków obcych za pomocą języka obcego. Przez to rozumiemy procesy twórcze, które obejmują rozumienie, analizę i ocenę treści tekstu w języku państwowym w celu wdrożenia próbki niezbędnych informacji i dalszej interpretacji. Osiągnięcie tych celów najlepiej pasuje do procesu wchłaniania tekstu w języku obcym, dlatego odniesienie jest kreatywnym językowym i intelektualnym procesem analitycznego przetwarzania informacji tekstowych na podstawie kompetencji mowy.

Celem artykułu jest ukazanie specyfiki odwoływania się do tekstów obcojęzycznych jako sposobu przetwarzania informacji i określenia metod nauczania odświeżających w instytucjach szkolnictwa wyższego.

Na podstawie przeprowadzonych badań ustalono, że proces szkolenia uchodźców powinien być ukierunkowany, spójny z pełną świadomością i dokładnym opracowaniem każdego etapu; odwoływanie się to racjonalna metoda przetwarzania treści tekstu, dlatego wskazane jest stosowanie następujących ćwiczeń podczas nauczania refleksologii: wybór słów kluczowych i zdań; odpowiedzi na pytania, które przyczyniają się do uogólnienia treści tekstu; uproszczenie struktury złożonych struktur; uogólnienie treści i alokacja głównej idei każdego akapitu; opracowanie logicznego planu tekstu; podział tekstu na wstęp, główną część i wniosek. Do prac przygotowawczych zalecano takie techniki, jak podział tekstu na fragmenty semantyczne, zapewnienie nagłówków tych fragmentów i sporządzenie planu; skrócenie tekstu; peryferie leksykalne, gramatyczne i półhore. Tak więc w procesie absorbowania tekstów obcojęzycznych u kandydatów następuje rozwój umiejętności czytania, mowy ustnej i pisemnej, zdolności analitycznych, krytycznych i twórczych. Zdobyte umiejętności i umiejętności naukowego przetwarzania tekstów umożliwiają wykorzystanie zagranicznych źródeł w procesie doskonalenia specjalności i promowania samodoskonalenia zawodowego.

Słowa kluczowe: abstrakcja, tekst w języku obcym, materiał językowy, algorytm abstrakcyjny, metody nauczania.

ABSTRACTING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEXTS AS A MEANS OF INFORMATION PROCESSING

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Abstract. One of the methods of foreign language teaching at higher educational establishments is the development of the skills of analytic and synthetic information processing by means of a foreign language. It deals with creative processes that include comprehension, analysis and assessment of the text content in the state language for the implementation of

selecting necessary information and further interpretation. The process of abstracting of a foreign language text corresponds to achievement of these goals, and therefore, abstracting is a creative linguistic and intellectual process of analytical processing of textual information based on speech competence.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the peculiarities of abstracting of a foreign language text as a means of information processing and to describe methods of its teaching at higher educational establishments.

On the basis of the conducted research it is established that the process of its teaching should be directed, consistent, with full awareness and thorough elaboration of each stage. Abstracting is a rational method of processing the content of the text, so it is expedient to use the following exercises when teaching to write abstracts: highlighting keywords and sentences; answers to questions that contribute to the synthesis of the text; simplifying the structure of complex common sentences; generalization of the content and selection of the main idea of each paragraph; drawing up a logical outline of the text; division of the text into the introduction, the main part and the conclusion. As a preparatory work, such techniques as dividing the text into semantic passages, heading these passages and drawing up a plan; abridgement of the text; lexical, grammatical and semantic paraphrase are recommended. Thus, in the process of abstracting foreign language texts, students develop their skills of reading, oral and written speech, analytical, critical and creative abilities. The acquired skills and abilities of scientific processing of texts make it possible to use foreign sources in the process of mastering the speciality and promote professional self-improvement.

Keywords: abstracting, foreign language text, language material, abstract algorithm, teaching methods.

РЕФЕРУВАННЯ ІНШОМОВНИХ ТЕКСТІВ ЯК ЗАСІБ ОБРОБКИ ІНФОРМАЦІЇ

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Анотація. Одним із методів навчання іноземної мови у немовних вузах є розвиток у здобувачів вищої освіти навичок аналітико-синтетичної обробки інформації засобами іноземної мови. Під цим ми розуміємо творчі процеси, що містять осмислення, аналіз та оцінку змісту тексту державною мовою для здійснення вибірки необхідних відомостей і подальший його усний переклад. Досягненню цих цілей найкраще відповідає процес реферування іноземного тексту, а отже, реферування – це креативний мовно-розумовий процес аналітичної переробки текстової інформації, що базується на мовленнєвій компетенції.

Мета статті – розкрити особливості реферування іноземних текстів як засобу обробки інформації та визначити методи навчання реферуванню у закладах вищої освіти.

На основі проведеного дослідження було встановлено, що процес навчання реферуванню має носити спрямований, послідовний характер із повним усвідомленням і ретельним опрацюванням кожного етапу; реферування є раціональним прийомом обробки змісту тексту, тому при навчанні реферуванню доцільно використовувати такі вправи: виділення ключових слів і речень; відповіді на питання, що сприяють узагальненню змісту тексту; спрощення структури складних конструкцій; узагальнення змісту і виділення головної думки кожного абзацу; складання логічного плану тексту; поділ тексту на вступ, основну частину і висновок. Для підготовчої роботи рекомендовано такі прийоми, як поділ тексту на смислові уривки, надання заголовків цих уривків і складання плану; скорочення

тексту; лексичний, граматичний і смисловий перифраз. Таким чином, у процесі реферування іншомовних текстів у здобувачів відбувається розвиток навичок читання, усного та писемного мовлення, аналітичних, критичних та творчих здібностей. А отримані навички та вміння наукової обробки текстів роблять можливим застосування іноземних джерел в процесі опанування спеціальності та сприяють професійному самовдосконаленню.

Ключові слова: реферування, іншомовний текст, мовний матеріал, алгоритм реферату, методи навчання.

Introduction

One of the methods of foreign language teaching at higher educational establishments is the development of the skills of analytic and synthetic information processing by means of a foreign language. It deals with creative processes that include comprehension, analysis and assessment of the text content in the state language for the implementation of selecting necessary information and further interpretation. The process of abstracting of a foreign language text corresponds to achievement of these goals.

The problem of abstracting of texts in foreign language teaching attracted the attention of many domestic and foreign scholars. In particular, it was studied by such scholars as C. Bernier, H. Borko (1975), R. Davis-Haley (2004), N. Fomenko (2004), V. Garkusheva, L. Piatnytska, L. Shamrai (2005), A. Konysheva, A. Veize (1997), N. Riabova (2002), H. Rogova (1991), N. Rybakova (2007), I. Zimnjaja (1992) and others.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the peculiarities of abstracting of a foreign language text as a means of information processing and to describe methods of its teaching at higher educational establishments.

1. The concept of "abstracting" in foreign language teaching

V. Slamecka (2018) states that in popular usage, the term information refers to facts and opinions provided and received during the course of daily life: one obtains information directly from other living beings, from mass media, from electronic data banks, and from all sorts of observable phenomena in the surrounding environment. A person using such facts and opinions generates more information, some of which is communicated to others during discourse, by instructions, in letters and documents, and through other media. Information organized according to some logical relationships is referred to as a body of knowledge, to be acquired by systematic exposure or study. Application of knowledge (or skills) yields expertise, and additional analytic or experiential insights are said to constitute instances of wisdom.

Yu. Kovalova (2010, p. 96–97) emphasizes that abstracting, first of all, is a creative linguistic and intellectual process of analytical processing of textual information based on speech competence. In this regard, the process of its teaching should be directed, consistent, with full awareness and thorough elaboration of each stage. Abstract teaching in a foreign language should be aimed at implementing the practical and educational goals creating a stable unity. Such implementation allows achieving a certain level of communicative competence, ensuring the practical use of language, attracting students to various sources of information, the perception of which is impossible without knowledge of language. It is necessary to take into consideration the requirements for the learning materials intended to form the

communicative competence: functionality (correlation with a certain sphere of communication); situationality (correspondence to the concrete situation of communication, which is imitated in the process of learning); thematicity (conformity with the program); stylistic diversity (use of various functional styles); reflection of the modern stage of the language (the need to use authentic texts functioning in real communication); saturation with socio-cultural facts (presence of socio-cultural realities and reflection of the characteristic features of speech behavior).

N. Rybakova (2007) notes that abstracting is a complex creative process built on the penetration in the essence of the statement. The process of abstracting is not just a reduction of the text, but a substantial rework of the content, composition and the language of the original:

- the text / article highlights the main content, which is expressed succinctly, briefly;

- if the main idea of the text / article is formulated not enough clearly, it should be specified and highlighted in the abstract;

- the same type of facts are grouped, then it gives a generalized characteristic;

- digitized data are systematized and generalized;

- in case of necessity, the timetable is moved in sequence from past to future;

- the language of the original text changes in the direction of normativity, neutrality, simplicity and concordance. Shaped expressions, epithets, introductory words, non-essential definitions, circumstances, and annexes are excluded. There is a reduction of complex syntactic constructions, reducing the number of additional sentences, replacing them with simpler phrases.

The text of the abstract displays the following data: the problem under study, the purpose, the main idea and the content of the work, the subject or purpose of the study; data on the methodology and its comparative precision; conclusions of the author and opportunities and ways of practical application of the results of work; references to bibliography and illustrative material; technology, applied equipment and research conditions; tables, diagrams, graphs, formulas needed to find out the main content of the document; necessary reference data. According to the specifics of the document, the abstract may not contain all of these data, but only a certain part of them.

Abstracting is a complex skill, consisting of a number of individual elements, which, during the entire course of studying English, aims at the following exercises:

- allocation of basic thoughts, facts, positions;

- selection of paragraphs containing basic information;

- heading of the selected paragraphs;

- drawing up an article plan;

- shortening the text;

- the transfer of the content of the text in their own words (paraphrase).

2. Methods of writing abstracts

Work on the writing of the abstract is carried out in accordance with the following algorithm:

- reviewing the text and familiarizing with its general content;

- more careful reading of the text, determining the sense of unfamiliar words by means of the context or a dictionary;

- semantic analysis of the text and distribution of the material of the article into three groups in terms of its importance: I group – the most important information that requires full and accurate reflection in the abstract; II group – secondary information transmitted in a shorter form; III group – insignificant information that can be omitted;

- organization of the selected material, linguistic processing and its presentation.

In the process of reading the text with its further abstracting it is possible to distinguish three main stages:

1. The stage of cognitive orientation in the text, that is, orientation in the text information in the form of "content grouping" and the selection of "content support points". Such a process consists of several steps:

a) scanning reading, which leads to the question of the expediency of abstracting a particular professional text. At this stage, students review the title, and then quickly read the text and determine the practical significance and informational novelty of the source. Key words must form a meaningful guideline that activates the further process of comprehension of the text;

b) selection of encyclopedic, branch dictionaries, reference and special literature, which can help in further work on the text;

c) analysis of the primary source and the choice of the aspect scheme of presentation of the material in the future abstract text.

2. The stage of reconstruction of the logical structure and generalization of perceived information. At this stage, there is a re-grouping of data by the degree of their significance and generalization of information at the level of the whole text. As a result, semi-productive transformations are carried out, with the help of which there is a compression of speech communication at the sentence level or part of it. This stage involves studying reading of the text. In this case, the student does not complete the full written translation of the text. Mental decoding of the foreign language text is carried out under the influence of a guide to abstract analysis. The need to highlight the aspects identified in the abstract plan activates the mental activity of the student and gives it a search character.

3. The stage of curtailing of generalized information to the level of the abstract. Here is the most intense meaningful re-encoding, which results in the compression of the original text at the semantic, lexical and grammatical levels. This step contains the following steps:

a) dividing the text into "aspect blocks";

b) construction (synthesis) of new statements in the native or foreign language, which should briefly and concisely convey the basic meaning of each aspect;

c) recordings of the statements received as a result of the above-mentioned transformations in the sequence given by the plan of the abstract;

d) critical comparison of the texts of the abstract with the original source and the introduction of changes and additions to the text of the abstract;

e) writing and wording of the abstract.

Thus, abstracting of a foreign language text requires the use of certain parts of the text, or meaningful interpretations of the text. The main thing is a selection of information relating to the main elements of the content of the text, and the most compact presentation of it. In addition, in the process of abstracting there is an exclusion of secondary, inessential facts that are not relevant to the object of research and its main characteristics. Therefore, the selection of the most important information and the

transfer of it in the form of an abstract are taken place. This is possible thanks to productive transformations as a result of meaningful perception of the text. They represent operations of curtailing the linguistic reflection and semantic content of the original text in the text of the abstract. As a result of reproductive transformations, abstracts-extracts, abstracts-citations are created. Semi-productive transformations correspond to abstracts-periphrasis, abstracts-generalizations (Shamraj, Garkusheva & Pjatnickaja, 2005).

The quality control of the practical application of the gained knowledge may be either current or final. For the purpose of final control, you can use the following types of abstracts: abstract-summary - a brief summary (conclusion) of the text, or abstract-synopsis - which is larger in volume and includes all the main statements of the original. Writing of narrative, informative or critical abstracts is offered as one of the varieties of independent work in preparation for the discussion of a particular professional topic. As homework, you may give to work out additional sources or study individual problems independently using one or several sources of information, and submit them in the form of an abstract.

For the purpose of current control, students can be offered the exercises that allow them to evaluate their comprehension skills, the selection of basic information and the ability to convey it in a concise form, for example:

- to formulate the basic idea of certain paragraphs of the text material in native or foreign languages;
- to give a title to each paragraph using or without using the words from this paragraph;
- to select sentences containing basic / additional information;
- to shorten sentences by means of specified words;
- to give answers to questions and make an annotation on their basis in a particular language, etc.

It should be noted that when evaluating abstract skills, one must take into account not only the final result of the work, but also a number of factors that directly affect the perception of the text material, namely:

- the socio-cultural level of each individual student;
- the degree of knowledge of a professional subject;
- the level of foreign language proficiency;
- the motivational basis for the student's work, which determines the degree of his activity.

Thus, the use of abstracting of foreign language texts as a form of current or final control has certain advantages that are reflected in the operational nature of this form of control, namely:

- 1) in accordance with the requirements for content and constructive validity;
- 2) in the efficiency of applied professional skills of analysis and systematization in solving problems;
- 3) in the possibility of combining the processes of education and training with self-education (Riabova, 2002).

M. Cohen-Vida (2012, p. 4984–4985) states that writing a good abstract does not mean just reducing a source text and replacing a word with another one, it means finding expressions to replace several relevant components of the original text. It is difficult to make a good abstract of a text when ignoring the subject matter. Experience shows that one does a good summary on a question that he/she knows well. Documentation is very

important when writing an abstract, as well as when translating a text. Writing a good abstract implies having good written expression abilities, being able to express another person's thinking in a concise manner and using a personal way of putting across the ideas of the source text. The scholar presents a number of techniques in order to develop students' skills of writing a good abstract. They are:

1. Abstract in one phrase

In order to write a good abstract, the students should be able to perceive the essential problem of the source text. That's why it is a profitable exercise to reduce the original text to one phrase. This phrase must not be inserted in the abstract at the beginning because it has to present the way of thinking of the author and it would be a mistake to anticipate from the first lines the conclusion of the text. It must not be inserted at the inner part of the abstract either. The students have to know that what they have obtained is not a phrase of the abstract but the axis around which the abstract should be organized.

2. Abstract based on the notes made on the text

For the long and complex texts a good method which precedes the writing of the abstract is to work on the text, to underline and frame certain elements of the original text. This work does not aim to bring up the elements which will be preserved in the abstract, after having changed a few of them, but it must bring up the structure of the original text.

Thus the following elements must be revealed by this work:

- The units of meaning;
- The connectors between these units;
- The connectors inside the units;
- The elements situated on the same level.
- The important elements are underlined;
- The connectors between the great units of meaning are to be framed by a rectangle, while the connectors inside the units will be put in parentheses (if there is a coherent text, the connectors are not so important, juxtaposition being enough to render the relations between the elements).
- The examples, the elements of an enumeration will be surrounded by a circle.
- The great units of meaning which do not necessarily coincide with the paragraphs are separated by a horizontal line, while a dotted line will mark a kind of break within the unit of meaning.

Using this system, the structure of the source text is brought forward, without overloading the text. Those who want to write a few words on the margins of the text are free to do so. As a result of this work, students establish the units of meaning of the source text, the relations between these units and because what they have now are no longer the paragraphs of the source text, but the paragraphs of the abstract. According to the number of words required, they will be able to write a good abstract.

3. Abstract based on the plan of the text

The abstract has a relatively reduced number of paragraphs. What students should know is that paragraphs have to be consistent, each of them corresponding to a unit of meaning. That is why, in order to determine the number of these units, students will find writing the plan of the text useful. For a while they leave their main goal – writing the abstract – in order to focus on the plan of the text (which will be the plan of the abstract, as well). This method allows students to 'rethink' the text and to 'reformulate' it. In

establishing the plan of a text, students are advised to look for the set of oppositions the text is based on, which also have to be found in the abstract.

4. Abstract based on the scheme of the text

It is possible, as well for long and complex texts, to visualize the structure of the text before starting to write the abstract. This method consists in establishing a very suggestive and relatively detailed scheme of the source text. The result will be a well-structured abstract in which the text is really rethought and reformulated, preserving the author's way of thinking and the characteristics of the text.

The best method of writing the abstract is established according to the characteristics of the source text, the required dimensions of the abstract and the students' own choice. More important than this option is the students' ability to understand the text and to re-express it in a concise way, preserving its distinctiveness.

Conclusions

Abstracting is a rational method of processing the content of the text, so it is expedient to use the following exercises when teaching to write abstracts: highlighting keywords and sentences; answers to questions that contribute to the synthesis of the text; simplifying the structure of complex common sentences; generalization of the content and selection of the main idea of each paragraph; drawing up a logical outline of the text; division of the text into the introduction, the main part and the conclusion. As a preparatory work, such techniques as dividing the text into semantic passages, heading these passages and drawing up a plan; abridgement of the text; lexical, grammatical and semantic paraphrase are recommended.

Thus, in the process of abstracting foreign language texts, students develop their skills of reading, oral and written speech, analytical, critical and creative abilities. The acquired skills and abilities of scientific processing of texts make it possible to use foreign sources in the process of mastering the speciality and promote professional self-improvement.

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